

Predicting Water Network Hydraulics: A Multi-Technique Exploration of Knowledge Transfer and Physics-Informed Machine Learning

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Abstract—Accurately predicting hydraulic behavior in Water Supply Systems (WSS) is fundamental for the maintenance of reliable operations, optimization of energy use, and control of maintenance costs. This study proposes a comparative study of several Machine Learning (ML) methodologies incorporating physics-informed, transfer learning, and ensemble techniques, to predict hydraulic behavior. Traditional hydraulic simulators, such as EPANET, typically rely on first principle hydraulic equations that may not capture real-world complexity. By integrating physical knowledge from multiple sources (e.g., EPANET output and simple mass conservation laws), the gap between predicted and observed behavior is minimized.

The techniques analyzed in this work were trained and tested on a real-world WSS dataset from a water network in Portugal. Results show that semi-supervised and ensemble techniques often deliver superior accuracy. It was evidenced that leveraging knowledge from diverse domains may boost the ML models capability to generalize in unseen data. It is also suggested that a tailored feature-by-feature importance weighting (in the output) leads to improved predictive performance.

Overall, this study offers practical guidance on the integration of physical-informed knowledge into the ML training process in complex and noisy systems. It is expected that the acquired observations lead to an increase in predictive capabilities applied in WSS or other systems.

This work is supported by the doctoral grant (Ref. 2023.01763.BDANA) financed by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) and by the projects: UIDB/00481/2020 and UIDP/00481/2020 - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, DOI 10.54499/UIDB/00481/2020 and DOI 10.54499/UIDP/00481/2020, and through the Regional Operational Program of the CenterRegion (CENTRO2030) within project I-ReTiS-LeaksD&Op(CENTRO2030-FEDER-01177300). This work has also received support from the Catalan Government under Project 2021 SGR 00197 and also by the Spanish Government under MICINN projects PID2019-105434RB-C33 co-funded with the European Union ERDF funds and MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 project TED2021-129134B-I00 co-funded with the European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR funds.

Index Terms—Machine Learning, Transfer Learning, Physics-Informed Machine Learning, Water Supply System

I. INTRODUCTION

Water Supply Systems (WSS) are one of the most important infrastructures in modern society, responsible for providing drinking water to all communities. Adequately managing a water network requires addressing its numerous facets, ranging from strategic infrastructure planning and leak detection to predictive maintenance and cost-efficient pump scheduling. In most of these tasks, the success of decisions depends on the accuracy of hydraulic models. Developing a reliable and accurate model to be used in a critical system, such as the WSS, is hindered by several challenges: unreliable/inaccurate sensors, degradation/malfunction of the infrastructure (e.g., pipe erosion or breakage), and/or the complexity of the hydraulic system itself. Existing hydraulic simulators, such as EPANET [1], combine the water network's topology with fundamental hydraulic equations, using real-world data to calibrate the necessary model coefficients. However, these simulators are grounded in idealized assumptions and often fail to capture the full extent of real-world behavior. Not only the data used for calibration is often noisy, incomplete, and not diverse (e.g., not in the full range of its pertinent features), these systems can also be non-stationary, i.e., change over time due to the gradual erosion of the infrastructure.

The motivation of this work is two-fold: developing a Machine Learning (ML) approach with higher accuracy in predicting the hydraulic behavior of a WSS, specifically predicting water tank levels and pump power given the current

system’s state; and understanding which methodology is optimal (and why) for the generalization in the current real-world case study. The methodologies explored are diverse and utilize concepts from the fields of Physics-Informed Machine Learning (PIML) and Domain Adaptation: Transfer Learning, PIML’s Learning Bias, semi-supervised ML, Knowledge Distillation, and ensemble methodologies. Additionally, as it will be clear in the following document, some methods can complement each other, creating hybrid methodologies.

This comparative study attempts to deconstruct how bias introduced by each approach results in ML models that can better generalize in unseen data. An analysis of the results is conducted on a feature-by-feature basis since each one is crucial in its prediction. Overall, this work explores the contributions of data-driven and physics-informed knowledge in learning hydraulic behaviors. The following research questions were made as the main guides for this study:

- Which methodology generally produces the most accurate results, and why?
- In what ways does each technique contribute to the improved predictive capability?

Finally, this work contributes to a broader effort of developing a Smart Predictive Digital Twin, where the best performing methodology in study will be used to produce the digital counterpart (i.e., Digital Model) of a WSS.

II. BACKGROUND

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN), also known as PIML, constitute a group of emerging techniques that aim to integrate external domain knowledge directly into the conventional ML training. As discussed in [2], PIML techniques can broadly be categorized by how bias is integrated in the learning process. Observational Bias involves augmenting the target (or real-world) dataset with simulated or synthetically generated data; Learning Bias integrates additional losses alongside the data-driven loss. Conventionally, these physics-informed losses are derived from physical laws (e.g., residuals calculated from governing physical laws). It can be argued that these losses can also be derived from other surrogate models that implicitly have physical patterns/knowledge; and Inductive Bias leverages architectures that are tailored to the data structure (e.g., using Convolutional Neural Networks for processing images).

In theory, PIML methodologies can be viewed as a form of Domain Adaptation, in which knowledge from a physical-informed domain (i.e., derived from simulated or expert knowledge) is transferred to a real-world target domain. This reframing allows leveraging hybrid ML approaches, such as Transfer Learning and Knowledge Distillation, which remain generally unexplored in WSS. Transfer Learning is a straightforward technique in which an ML model is firstly trained on a source domain and then is finetuned on data from the target domain. A brief example of this in the WSS is presented in the work [3], where an ML model was trained on data synthetically generated by EPANET, and was subsequently trained on the target domain. Knowledge Distillation [4] transfers

knowledge from a teacher ML model (i.e., a pretrained model) to a student ML model. Although this latter methodology is usually applied to generate a smaller/simpler ML models, it is often observed an increase in accuracy on unseen data. This behavior has been explored more in-depth in [5].

Despite PIML’s broad success, its application in hydraulic systems remains scarce. For instance, the work in [6] used PIML to predict pressures during hydraulic transients in unmonitored pipes, and the work in [7] combined physical insights with Graph Convolutional Networks to estimate hydraulic states.

III. TRAINING PREPARATION

A. Datasets

1) *Real-world Dataset*: In this study, data was collected from sensors of a WSS located in Portugal, between January 11st to July 13rd of 2023 with a resolution of 15 minutes. This water network, denominated henceforth as **Ro**, comprises six water pumps, one binary valve, six water tanks, and eight water demand nodes. The topology of this water network is represented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Topology of the **Ro** water network. The letters correspond to the name of locations and will be used to reference the directly connected water tanks.

As is often the case in real-world environments, the collected data is noisy, has missing values in some data samples, and some necessary features to train the ML model are not explicitly available. To address the noise, exponential smoothing was applied. Data samples with missing features are removed, reducing the size of the original dataset to 9145 samples. The full preprocessing implementation is detailed in the work [3].

In this work, the training of ML models requires pump power and the valve status data, but these features are not explicitly available on the dataset. To solve this, other features were used to indirectly calculate these target features. The original dataset has available the flow rate in each pump, which subsequently can be used with the corresponding pump power curves to calculate the pump power. It’s important to note that while the pump power is based on real data, its equation-based representation introduces some deviation from real-world behavior. However, since pump power values are either zero or close to a reference point, this deviation is limited and can be neglected. Regarding the valve operation

in the network, its operation is based on specific event-based rules: it opens when the **E** water tank’s level is below 2.25 meters, and it closes when it goes over 2.27 meters or if the **A2** water tank’s level goes below 2.254 meters. With these rules, it is possible to infer the status of the valve by the behavior of the aforementioned water tank levels.

Because the resulting real-world dataset is limited in its size, only a single day of continuous hydraulic behavior (96 samples) was allocated exclusively for cross-testing. From the remaining data, 10% is set aside as the Test Dataset. The rest is randomly split in each training loop, with 20% allocated for validation and the remainder for training.

2) *EPANET*: A calibrated EPANET hydraulic simulator of this specific water network is available. The calibration process calculates coefficients of the hydraulic equations that better capture the observed behavior, effectively making this hydraulic simulator an equation-based representation, albeit in a simplified sense. Real-world data was used to calibrate EPANET (not the data introduced in this work), which includes more features than the ones already presented, such as pressure and flow rate.

A dataset of 30k samples is generated using the EPANET simulator. This dataset will be referred to as the Synthetic Dataset, and is used primarily to train a surrogate ML model (i.e., pretrained ML model). To simplify subsequent discussions, the physics-informed knowledge acquired by training the pretrained model on the Synthetic Dataset will be referred to as EPANET’s physics-informed knowledge.

B. Training Procedure

All methodologies presented in this work utilize the same features for training. The input features comprise the water demands, actuator status, and water tank levels. Output features are the rate of change of the corresponding water tank levels and pump powers (differential outputs).

Since this is a comparative work, it is essential to ensure a fair performance comparison between methodologies. To produce statistically significant results, each methodology was applied 20 times, with the training and validation data randomly split in each run. Furthermore, to guarantee that the only differences in performance are from the methodologies themselves and not from the data used for training, each run has a unique random seed, which is shared by all methodologies. This allows for each methodology to use the same 20 random train-validation splits. Finally, since each methodology has unique characteristics and varying numbers of hyperparameters, a dedicated hyperparameter tuning process is conducted for each method. This ensures that every methodology is evaluated at its optimal performance, allowing for a fair comparison of their full potential. A Bayesian Optimization [8] was used to efficiently explore the search space, while Hyperband [9] was employed as an early stopping approach.

Henceforth, for organizational purposes, the developed methodologies are categorized within three main groups. The Vanilla Group comprises all the standalone methodologies (except for the Ensemble Methodology) without the addition of

any other ML techniques. The Transfer Learning Group refers to the aforementioned methodologies enhanced by initializing the training with a pretrained model, i.e., transfer learning. Finally, the ML models obtained from the Transfer Learning are used as Teacher ML models in the zero-shot Knowledge Distillation technique. Subsequently, ML models resulting from the process are part of the Knowledge Distillation Group.

IV. METHODOLOGIES

This section presents the methodologies analyzed and compared in this work. It’s important to note that the **Baseline** methodology specifically serves as reference, representing a scenario with no integration of additional techniques. Thus, it can be a direct means to compare the performance of other methodologies.

A. Baseline

The Baseline method refers to the traditional training loop using solely the Real-World Dataset. The training process exclusively includes the data-driven loss function $Loss_{data-driven}$, which calculates the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the ground-truth and predicted values:

$$Loss_{data-driven} = L(Y, \hat{Y}), \quad (1)$$

where L^1 represents the error calculation function, Y are the ground-truth values and \hat{Y} are the ML model’s predicted values.

B. Transfer Learning

In this work, an ML model, named $Surrogate_{ML}$, is trained on the Synthetic Dataset to capture useful patterns (i.e., shared patterns between domains). Subsequently, this ML model is then used as a starting point of the next training process, leveraging prior knowledge which potentially enhances performance. This methodology can be applied in conjunction with any other methodology proposed in this work.

C. PIML’s Learning Bias from Surrogate

The most straightforward application of PIML techniques is the usage of the Learning Bias to integrate in the training both the data-driven and physics-informed patterns. The most common approach is to directly use a Physical-Informed Loss, $Loss_{PIML}$, alongside the data-driven loss. Typically, this added loss is derived from residual equations, but here the outputs of $Surrogate_{ML}$ are used to calculate this loss:

$$Loss_{PIML} = L(\tilde{Y}, \hat{Y}), \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{Y} is the $Surrogate_{ML}$ ’s output. The total loss function is then:

$$Loss_{Total} = (1 - \alpha) \cdot Loss_{data} + \alpha \cdot Loss_{Physics}, \quad (3)$$

¹Throughout the work L is the MSE metric function.

where α is a hyperparameter controlling the balance between these two losses. Instead of a fixed α throughout training, multiple values are assigned at specific epochs (equally spaced), with the final value set to zero (i.e., no physical-informed contribution). Intermediate α values are interpolated by using a spline function. Hyperparameter tuning consistently indicated a prioritization of the data-driven loss in the early stage of the training process.

This methodology, named **Surrogate ML model Learning Bias**, initially used EPANET but it underperformed greatly. It is suspected that EPANET's inability to apply backpropagation hindered learning. In contrast, an ML model, despite having fixed parameters, provides gradients beneficial for the target model's optimization.

D. PIML's Learning Bias from Residual Equation

The usage of residual equations directly in loss functions is the most common PIML approach. This allows the ML model to capture underlying physical patterns between features. This methodology is named **Residual Equation Learning Bias**, where its corresponding loss can be represented as follows:

$$Loss_{Total} = (1 - \alpha) \cdot Loss_{data} + \alpha \cdot R(X)^2, \quad (4)$$

where $R(X)$ is the residual equation function, which incorporates mass conservation laws applied to this hydraulic system. These equations represent the inflow, outflow, and storage of water in tanks, within certain regions of the water network. To showcase the formulation of the residual equation, the branch leading to \mathbf{T} is exemplified. This particular branch has pump P_T , water demand node, Q_{J10} , and the water tank, h_T . The water inflow, Q_{in} , outflow, Q_{out} , and storage, Q_{Tank} , are defined as follows:

$$Q_{in} = Q_{PumpTrav}, \quad Q_{out} = Q_{J10}, \quad Q_{Tank} = A_{Tank} \frac{\partial h_{Tank}}{\partial t}, \quad (5)$$

where A_{Tank} is the water reservoir's area, necessary to calculate the water flow rate going in or out of the tank, and t is the time variable. The residual equation of this particular branch can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{in} = Q_{Tank} + Q_{out} &\Leftrightarrow Q_{PumpT} = A_{Tank} \frac{\partial h_{Tank}}{\partial t} + Q_{J10} \\ \Leftrightarrow 0 &= A_{Tank} \frac{\partial h_{Tank}}{\partial t} + Q_{J10} - Q_{PumpT}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The residual equation takes as input the water demand at junction 10, the tank's rate of change (from prediction), and the water flow in the pump. This approach requires establishing a mapping between the pump power and the corresponding flow rate, which is achieved through a polynomial approximation. In this particular case study, flow rate data is available but was not included in the mentioned datasets. Mapping pump power directly to the flow rate can present a challenge because, under certain conditions, a single pump power can correspond to two distinct flow rates. Subsequently, this leads to a non-functional

mapping unsuitable for direct function approximations. To address this, a portion of data was removed, which allowed approximating the pump power and flow rate relationship through a polynomial function.

A residual equation was calculated for each branch in the water network. Although this methodology is inspired by PIML methodologies, it is impractical for larger WSS.

E. Semi-Supervised ML

A set of Semi-Supervised methodologies is proposed where they integrate Observational Bias and Learning Bias simultaneously. The training process consists of two learning stages, which are randomly alternated between each other. A Real-world learning stage trains the target ML model with the Real-world dataset alongside a Learning Bias using $Surrogate_{ML}$ to generate the Physical-Informed loss. In contrast, the Synthetic Learning Stage has only the Physical-Informed loss, using randomly generated data as input for both the $Surrogate_{ML}$ and the target ML model. In the latter stage, using randomly generated data as input serves as a proxy to directly learning the $Surrogate_{ML}$ behavior.

It is expected that by alternating between these two learning stages the ML model will be capable of capturing enriched data-driven and Physical-informed patterns. Similarly to the **Surrogate ML model Learning Bias** methodology, there is an α hyperparameter which changes over time. A β hyperparameter is also included which indicates the probability of switching to the Synthetic Learning Stage.

The **Semi-Supervised EPANET Surrogate** and **Semi-Supervised ML Model Surrogate** methodologies were applied, which use EPANET and ML models as surrogate models, respectively. During development, integrating external knowledge improved the prediction of certain features while others remained unchanged or underperformed. To address this, the **Semi-Supervised Alphas** methodology is introduced, using an ML model as a surrogate and assigning individual loss weights to each feature. These weights determine the importance of each metric during training. In this approach, β varies throughout training, similar to α .

F. Knowledge Distillation

As mentioned in the state-of-the-art section, Knowledge Distillation is an ML technique conventionally used to decrease the size of the ML model without a decrease (or with minor decrease) in performance. This methodology was explored in an attempt to improve the performance of ML models in unseen data. It was opted for a zero-shot data Knowledge Distillation, which consists of using only randomly generated data as the input for both the Teacher and Student models and the corresponding Teacher's output as the target labels for the Student Model.

G. Ensemble Methods

The evaluation of metrics on validation and test datasets reveals that each methodology slightly improves performance for specific features. To leverage this, an ensemble methodology is implemented, where the top four performing models

for each output feature are combined using a weighted mean. The contribution of each model is determined by its performance (using the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)) on the validation set, with weights normalized across all models.

The main downside of this approach is its computational cost. Since six output features are predicted using four models each, inference requires a maximum of 24 ML models, making this method impractical for computationally demanding tasks, such as applying hydraulic state estimation for model predictive control.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although the training process includes the prediction of both the rate of change of water tank levels and pump power, the latter was omitted from the results and discussion, since corresponding predictions remained adequate for practical applications and the ML models exhibited minimal variation. The Knowledge Distillation Group underperformed greatly on the Test Dataset and was removed from most of the discussion to improve visualization of figures and focus of the remainder of the methodologies/Groupings.

From Figure 2 it is evident that overall Transfer Learning didn't result in a significant increase in performance. Broadly, it underperformed on features **A2** and **E**, overperformed on features **A1** and **T**, and the performance remained somewhat neutral on the other features. It's worth highlighting that among all methodologies, the **Residual Equation Learning Bias** consistently improves performance when Transfer Learning is applied across all features. Even in the worst case, its performance remains unaffected rather than deteriorating.

Figure 3 illustrates a macro view of the performance of each methodology and Group on each feature. First of all, it is unsurprising that the **Ensemble** methodology generally outperforms other approaches, being matched in performance by other methodologies in features **A2**, **S**, and **C**. It's interesting to note that in the features (i.e., **T** and **A1**) where Transfer Learning generally increased performance, are also the same Features in which **Residual Equation Learning Bias** underperformed greatly. This can be an indication that the more the behavior of the real-world water tank levels is similar to the EPANET's model, the worse the bias injected by **Residual Equation Learning Bias** makes the ML model gen-

Fig. 2. Comparison between Vanilla and Transfer Learning Groups on various methodologies. Each subplot focuses on a specific target feature (labeled at the top-left). The x-axis and y-axis show the normalized RMSE of that feature under, respectively, a Vanilla training setup and a Transfer Learning setup. Normalization is computed per feature, using all runs of that feature. The colored points represent model performances across the same train-validation splits, with each color indicating a specific methodology: ■ Baseline, ■ Surrogate ML (EPANET-based), ■ Equation Residual, ■ Semi-Supervised EPANET Surrogate, ■ Semi-Supervised ML Surrogate, and ■ Semi-Supervised Alphas. For each methodology, the star symbol indicates the mean performance across all runs of that methodology. Points below the diagonal ($y=x$) imply that Transfer Learning improves performance compared to the Vanilla Group.

Fig. 3. Performance comparison of proposed methodologies and Groups. Each subplot focuses on a specific target feature (labeled at the top-left). The y axis is the RMSE of that feature, and x axis is each methodology. The colored boxplots correspond to the Vanilla and Transfer Learning Groups. The Ensemble methodology is uniquely color coded since it's not from either the previous groups. The \bullet symbol corresponds to outliers automatically generated by the boxplots.

eralyze. Simultaneously, this can be evidence that EPANET's calibration is close to the real hydraulic behavior at least on these aforementioned water tanks.

Apart from the **Ensemble** methodology, the **Semi-Supervised Alphas** approach consistently achieves the best performance, except in the case of feature **S**. This improvement is likely due to the assignment of individual weights to each feature, which helps account for deviations in hydraulic behavior of each water tank compared to the assumptions made by the EPANET simulator. The main downside of this methodology is the need for a longer running hyperparameter tuning, since there is an addition of an hyperparameter for each output feature.

In general, the Semi-Supervised approaches had a better performance than the **Baseline**, **Residual Equation Learning Bias**, and **Surrogate ML Model Learning Bias**. This is indicative of the superior performance that the proposed Semi-Supervised approaches provide in this particular case study. An exception of its higher performance occurs in feature **C**, where any attempt to inject physical-informed knowledge, derived from EPANET, resulted in performances inferior to the **Baseline** methodology. In this case, the **Residual Equations Learning Bias** methodology had the best performance, surpassing the **Baseline**. It can be concluded that the real-world hydraulic behavior in this particular tank approximated more closely to the simplified residual equations than the EPANET's knowledge. All the methodologies' performance acquired from

the Test Dataset is summarized in Table I.

The Cross-Test Dataset consists of only 96 samples, which limits the statistical significance of any analysis of the effectiveness of the proposed methodologies. ML models were provided with an initial water tank level and tasked with predicting 24-hour tank levels based solely on that initial value, along with water demand and pump status, reflecting a typical application of these models in a real WSS scenario. At each time step, the ML model's output is integrated in time (because the outputs are the rate of change of water tank levels), and is subsequently used as input in the next time step.

As mentioned, the Knowledge Distillation resulted in underperformed ML models, and was even removed from most figures to allow for a more suitable visualization of the rest of the methodologies (i.e., the axis y would be too large and other boxplots would be too small). That remains true, when calculating the ML models' errors when applied to the Cross-Test Dataset, with the exception in **A1** (see Figure 5). It must be reiterated that the ML model is being tested on solely 96 samples, but this behavior is consistent among all the other methodologies in this particular feature, making it noteworthy. It can be argued that Knowledge Distillation in regression problems behaves like a regularizer, creating ML models with "smoother" outputs. The smoothing effect from Knowledge Distillation may be particularly beneficial for predicting this specific feature, either due to unique conditions on this selected day or because iterative predictions benefit

TABLE I

PERFORMANCE OF METHODOLOGIES AND GROUPS, ACROSS FEATURES, USING RMSE AND R^2 METRICS. FOR EACH FEATURE, THE BEST OVERALL METRIC IS HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD, AND THE BEST METRIC FROM STANDALONE METHODOLOGIES IS UNDERLINED.

Method	Groups	A2		T		C		S		A1		E	
		RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2
Baseline	Vanilla	1.42×10^{-5} $\pm 3.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.896 ± 0.005	7.3×10^{-6} $\pm 7.2 \times 10^{-8}$	0.971± 0.000 58	1.83×10^{-5} $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	0.785 ± 0.024	9.42×10^{-6} $\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-6}$	0.975± 0.0086	7.54×10^{-6} $\pm 6.8 \times 10^{-8}$	0.938± 0.0011	1.16×10^{-5} $\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.628± 0.0099
	Transfer Learning	1.44×10^{-5} $\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-7}$	0.892± 0.0054	7.22×10^{-6} $\pm 5.6 \times 10^{-8}$	0.971± 0.000 43	1.75×10^{-5} $\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.803 ± 0.022	8.03×10^{-6} $\pm 8.9 \times 10^{-7}$	0.983± 0.0041	7.47×10^{-6} $\pm 7.4 \times 10^{-8}$	0.939± 0.0012	1.18×10^{-5} $\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.612 ± 0.017
	Knowledge Distillation	1.77×10^{-5} $\pm 9.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.837 ± 0.018	9.24×10^{-6} $\pm 8.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.953± 0.0086	4.51×10^{-5} $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$	-0.397 ± 0.66	1.47×10^{-5} $\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-6}$	0.941 ± 0.015	7.8×10^{-6} $\pm 3.0 \times 10^{-7}$	0.934± 0.0054	1.45×10^{-5} $\pm 9.7 \times 10^{-7}$	0.412 ± 0.08
Surrogate ML Model Learning Bias	Vanilla	1.44×10^{-5} $\pm 4.7 \times 10^{-7}$	0.893± 0.0071	7.57×10^{-6} $\pm 2.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.969± 0.0023	1.99×10^{-5} $\pm 5.4 \times 10^{-6}$	0.728 ± 0.19	7.77×10^{-6} $\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-6}$	0.983± 0.0063	7.71×10^{-6} $\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$	0.935± 0.0028	1.18×10^{-5} $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.614 ± 0.023
	Transfer Learning	1.44×10^{-5} $\pm 5.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.893± 0.0081	7.59×10^{-6} $\pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.968 ± 0.002	1.85×10^{-5} $\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-6}$	0.779 ± 0.043	7.19×10^{-6} $\pm 9.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.986± 0.0036	7.61×10^{-6} $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-7}$	0.937± 0.0017	1.19×10^{-5} $\pm 4.7 \times 10^{-7}$	0.607 ± 0.031
	Knowledge Distillation	1.93×10^{-5} $\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-6}$	0.804 ± 0.032	8.47×10^{-6} $\pm 6.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.96± 0.006	4.27×10^{-5} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-5}$	-0.249 ± 0.6	1.63×10^{-5} $\pm 4.0 \times 10^{-6}$	0.925 ± 0.033	8.15×10^{-6} $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.928± 0.0063	1.54×10^{-5} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$	0.336 ± 0.096
Residual Equation Learning Bias	Vanilla	1.43×10^{-5} $\pm 4.6 \times 10^{-7}$	0.893± 0.0069	7.52×10^{-6} $\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.969± 0.0017	1.61×10^{-5} <u>$\pm 8.8 \times 10^{-7}$</u>	0.832 ± 0.018	7.12×10^{-6} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$	0.986± 0.0038	7.86×10^{-6} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.933± 0.0018	1.18×10^{-5} $\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.609 ± 0.015
	Transfer Learning	1.43×10^{-5} $\pm 3.9 \times 10^{-7}$	0.894± 0.0058	7.51×10^{-6} $\pm 1.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.969± 0.0011	1.63×10^{-5} $\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.829 ± 0.019	7.16×10^{-6} $\pm 6.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.986± 0.0024	7.76×10^{-6} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.935± 0.0019	1.17×10^{-5} $\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.616 ± 0.015
	Knowledge Distillation	1.76×10^{-5} $\pm 6.6 \times 10^{-7}$	0.839 ± 0.012	9.42×10^{-6} $\pm 5.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.951± 0.0055	3.35×10^{-5} $\pm 7.6 \times 10^{-6}$	0.242 ± 0.35	1.57×10^{-5} $\pm 2.7 \times 10^{-6}$	0.932 ± 0.022	7.92×10^{-6} $\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.932± 0.0035	1.47×10^{-5} $\pm 9.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.395 ± 0.083
Semi Supervised EPANET Surrogate	Vanilla	1.39×10^{-5} $\pm 4.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.899± 0.0062	7.29×10^{-6} $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.971± 0.000 97	2.24×10^{-5} $\pm 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$	0.676 ± 0.07	1.17×10^{-5} $\pm 3.2 \times 10^{-6}$	0.961 ± 0.018	7.52×10^{-6} $\pm 8.5 \times 10^{-8}$	0.939± 0.0014	1.14×10^{-5} $\pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.638 ± 0.015
	Transfer Learning	1.41×10^{-5} $\pm 3.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.897± 0.0055	7.23×10^{-6} $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.971± 0.000 98	2.33×10^{-5} $\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-6}$	0.649 ± 0.07	1.13×10^{-5} $\pm 2.6 \times 10^{-6}$	0.964 ± 0.014	7.47×10^{-6} $\pm 5.8 \times 10^{-8}$	0.939± 0.000 94	1.15×10^{-5} $\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.632 ± 0.014
	Knowledge Distillation	1.98×10^{-5} $\pm 6.7 \times 10^{-7}$	0.797 ± 0.014	8.54×10^{-6} $\pm 5.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.96± 0.0056	0.000 112 $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-5}$	-7.87 ± 5	1.98×10^{-5} $\pm 6.8 \times 10^{-6}$	0.883 ± 0.073	8.11×10^{-6} $\pm 3.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.929± 0.0055	1.56×10^{-5} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$	0.318 ± 0.094
Semi Supervised ML Model Surrogate	Vanilla	1.39×10^{-5} $\pm 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$	0.9± 0.0058	7.38×10^{-6} $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.97± 0.000 99	2.23×10^{-5} $\pm 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$	0.671 ± 0.13	5.62×10^{-6} $\pm 5.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.991± 0.0015	7.54×10^{-6} $\pm 8.7 \times 10^{-8}$	0.938± 0.0014	1.14×10^{-5} $\pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.637 ± 0.015
	Transfer Learning	1.41×10^{-5} $\pm 4.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.897± 0.0064	7.28×10^{-6} $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$	0.971± 0.000 93	2.15×10^{-5} $\pm 4.1 \times 10^{-6}$	0.693 ± 0.12	5.43×10^{-6} <u>$\pm 3.7 \times 10^{-7}$</u>	0.992 ± 0.001	7.52×10^{-6} $\pm 5.8 \times 10^{-8}$	0.939± 0.000 95	1.16×10^{-5} $\pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.627 ± 0.016
	Knowledge Distillation	2.15×10^{-5} $\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$	0.757 ± 0.053	8.49×10^{-6} $\pm 7.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.96± 0.0073	6.59×10^{-6} $\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$	-2.2 ± 2.3	2.57×10^{-5} $\pm 6.5 \times 10^{-6}$	0.812 ± 0.083	8.06×10^{-6} $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.929± 0.0063	1.9×10^{-5} $\pm 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$	-0.0135 ± 0.22
Semi Supervised Alphas	Vanilla	1.35×10^{-5} $\pm 4.3 \times 10^{-7}$	0.905 ± 0.006	7.09×10^{-6} $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-8}$	<u>0.972±</u> 0.000 27	2.6×10^{-5} $\pm 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$	0.557 ± 0.13	6.26×10^{-6} $\pm 9.0 \times 10^{-7}$	0.989± 0.0029	7.39×10^{-6} $\pm 4.0 \times 10^{-8}$	0.941± 0.000 65	1.13×10^{-5} $\pm 3.1 \times 10^{-7}$	0.644 ± 0.019
	Transfer Learning	1.35×10^{-5} $\pm 4.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.905± 0.0064	7.09×10^{-6} $\pm 4.1 \times 10^{-8}$	<u>0.972±</u> 0.000 32	2.55×10^{-5} $\pm 3.3 \times 10^{-6}$	0.575 ± 0.1	6.47×10^{-6} $\pm 9.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.989± 0.0032	7.36×10^{-6} <u>$\pm 3.7 \times 10^{-8}$</u>	0.941± 0.000 59	1.14×10^{-5} $\pm 2.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.641 ± 0.018
	Knowledge Distillation	2.31×10^{-5} $\pm 1.6 \times 10^{-6}$	0.722 ± 0.038	7.89×10^{-6} $\pm 2.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.966± 0.0025	0.000 113 $\pm 3.6 \times 10^{-5}$	-7.97 ± 4.6	3.27×10^{-5} $\pm 6.2 \times 10^{-6}$	0.703 ± 0.093	7.68×10^{-6} $\pm 1.8 \times 10^{-7}$	0.936 ± 0.003	1.98×10^{-5} $\pm 3.3 \times 10^{-6}$	-0.124 ± 0.42
Ensemble	1.23×10^{-5} $\pm 3.5 \times 10^{-7}$	0.906± 0.0048	7.03×10^{-6} $\pm 2.8 \times 10^{-8}$	0.973± 0.000 21	1.66×10^{-5} $\pm 9.4 \times 10^{-7}$	0.823 ± 0.02	6.1×10^{-6} $\pm 1.3 \times 10^{-6}$	0.99± 0.0043	7.36×10^{-6} $\pm 4.5 \times 10^{-8}$	0.941± 0.000 72	1.11×10^{-5} $\pm 2.0 \times 10^{-7}$	0.654 ± 0.013	

from smoother model outputs.

Regarding Figure 4, the top three best performing methodologies on the Test Dataset on each feature were selected to be applied to the Cross-Test Dataset, alongside the real behavior, EPANET, and the Ensemble methodology. The order of the chosen methodologies is often not aligned with their performance in this dataset. For instance, in feature C, it is visually recognizable that the **Residual Equations Learning Bias** has the most substantial deviation from the real-world behavior even though it should be the top performing. It is noteworthy that EPANET's 24-hour time-horizon predictions often outperform other methods, as illustrated in the case of features E, S, and A2. Interestingly, EPANET underperforms significantly on features T and A1, which are the same features where Transfer Learning shows improved performance. Paradoxically, features S and E see a decrease in performance when Transfer Learning is applied. This phenomenon can either be from local conditions specific to the selected day or from the cumulative effects introduced by the autoregressive nature of predictions in the cross-test scenario.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This comparative study provides key insights into the effectiveness of integrating physics-informed knowledge into ML

models in improving predictive capabilities in WSS. Notably, it was observed that the semi-supervised approach demonstrated improved performance. Hence, it can be concluded that alternating between learning stages (i.e., different sources of information while using learning bias) throughout the training process potentially augments the learning of useful physical-informed and data-driven patterns. Additionally, it was evidenced that each output feature is associated with a certain degree of proximity to the physical-informed contribution. This in turn signifies how well the simulated/expert knowledge is aligned with the real-world behavior. By assigning feature-specific weights to the outputs the generalization capability of the model is enhanced. This is supported by **Semi-Supervised Alphas** having the best performance in general. Lastly, leveraging multiple sources of domain knowledge, such as EPANET simulations and simplified hydraulic equations, can potentially prove beneficial as the real-world behavior can align with either of these approximations.

These findings highlight the advantages of integrating data-driven learning alongside physical-informed knowledge to improve knowledge in complex physical systems. This comparative study offers practical guidelines for selecting and effectively combining different sources of knowledge to improve predictive modeling in complex physical systems.

Fig. 4. Comparison between methodologies' ML models in predicting water tank levels in 24-hour time-horizon, with the water demands, pump statuses, and initial water tank level available. Each subplot focuses on a specific feature (labeled at the top-left corner). Besides the labeled methodology in each subplot the █ ground-truth behavior is also represented, alongside the █ Ensemble methodology and █ EPANET's prediction

Fig. 5. Performance comparison of proposed methodologies and Groups in feature A1. The y axis is the RMSE between ground-truth and prediction in that feature, and x axis is each methodology. The colored boxplots correspond to the █ Vanilla, █ Transfer Learning, and █ Knowledge Distillation Groups. The █ Ensemble methodology is uniquely colored. The ● symbol corresponds to outliers automatically generated by the boxplots.

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